

Appendix

A. The Global Optimum of Criterion (8)

In this section, we derive the global optimum of the training criterion (8), and show that this is equivalent to the ILM definition in Eq. (5). In order to distinguish a complete sequence and a prefix, we write out the $\langle \text{EOS} \rangle$ label explicitly. To simplify the discussion, we assume that the maximum sequence length is finite. Therefore, all summations are done over a finite set, and exchanging the order of summations is always possible. Assume an unlimited amount of training data so that empirical distributions are the same as true distributions, i.e. $\tilde{Pr}(\cdot) = Pr(\cdot)$. We have:

$$\begin{aligned}
F(\theta) &= \\
&= \sum_{s,X,a_1^S} Pr(X, a_1^S \cdot \langle \text{EOS} \rangle) \sum_{s=1}^{S+1} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{V}^+} P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X) \log \frac{P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X)}{q_\theta(a|a_1^{s-1})} \\
&= \sum_S \sum_{s=1}^{S+1} \sum_{X, a_1^S} Pr(X, a_1^S \cdot \langle \text{EOS} \rangle) \sum_{a \in \mathcal{V}^+} P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X) \log \frac{P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X)}{q_\theta(a|a_1^{s-1})} \\
&= \sum_S \sum_{s=1}^{S+1} \sum_{X, a_1^{s-1}} Pr(X, a_1^{s-1}) \cdot \sum_{a_s^S} Pr(a_s^S \cdot \langle \text{EOS} \rangle | a_1^{s-1}, X) \\
&\quad \cdot \sum_{a \in \mathcal{V}^+} P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X) \log \frac{P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X)}{q_\theta(a|a_1^{s-1})} \\
&= \sum_{X, s, a_1^{s-1}} Pr(X, a_1^{s-1}) \sum_{a \in \mathcal{V}^+} P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X) \log \frac{P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X)}{q_\theta(a|a_1^{s-1})} \\
&\quad \cdot \underbrace{\sum_{S \geq s-1, a_s^S} Pr(a_s^S \cdot \langle \text{EOS} \rangle | a_1^{s-1}, X)}_{= 1 \text{ c.f. the normalization of } Pr(\cdot | a_1^{s-1}, X), \text{ } a_s^{s-1} \text{ refers to an empty sequence}} \\
&= \sum_{X, s, a_1^{s-1}} Pr(X, a_1^{s-1}) \sum_{a \in \mathcal{V}^+} P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X) \log \frac{P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X)}{q_\theta(a|a_1^{s-1})} \\
&= \sum_{s, a_1^{s-1}} Pr(a_1^{s-1}) \sum_{a \in \mathcal{V}^+} \sum_X P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X) Pr(X|a_1^{s-1}) \log \frac{P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X)}{q_\theta(a|a_1^{s-1})} \tag{12}
\end{aligned}$$

Since $\sum_X P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X) Pr(X|a_1^{s-1})$ is a properly normalized distribution over $a \in \mathcal{V}^+$, according to Gibbs' inequality, the global optimum of Eq. (12) is obtained via:

$$\hat{q}_\theta(a|a_1^{s-1}) = \sum_X P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X) Pr(X|a_1^{s-1}), \forall a \in \mathcal{V}^+$$

Namely, equivalent to the definition Eq. (5)

B. Equivalence between Eq. (9) and (10)

Here, we derive that Eq. (9) is equivalent to Eq. (10). By definition, the empirical distributions are computed via:

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{Pr}(X, a_1^S) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \delta(X, X_n) \delta(a_1^S, a_{n,1}^{S_n}), \\
\tilde{Pr}(X) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \delta(X, X_n), \quad \tilde{Pr}(a_1^S) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \delta(a_1^S, a_{n,1}^{S_n})
\end{aligned}$$

To simplify notations, we define

$$G(P, q|X, a_1^S) := \sum_{s=1}^{S+1} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{V}^+} P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X) \log \frac{P(a|a_1^{s-1}, X)}{q_\theta(a|a_1^{s-1})}$$

Therefore, Eq. (9) can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned}
F(\theta) &= \sum_{X, s, a_1^S} \overline{Pr}(X, a_1^S) G(P, q|X, a_1^S) \\
&= \sum_{s, X, a_1^S} \frac{\alpha}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \delta(a_1^S, a_{n,1}^{S_n}) \delta(X, X_n) G(P, q|X, a_1^S) \\
&\quad + \sum_{s, X, a_1^S} \frac{1-\alpha}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \delta(a_1^S, a_{n,1}^{S_n}) \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n'=1}^N \delta(X, X_{n'}) G(P, q|X, a_1^S) \\
&= \frac{\alpha}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{(X, a_1^S): X=X_n, a_1^S=a_{n,1}^{S_n}} G(P, q|X, a_1^S) \\
&\quad + \frac{1-\alpha}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{a_1^S: a_1^S=a_{n,1}^{S_n}} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n'=1}^N \sum_{X: X=X_{n'}} G(P, q|X, a_1^S) \\
&= \frac{\alpha}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N G(P, q|X_n, a_{n,1}^{S_n}) + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{n'=1}^N \frac{1-\alpha}{N} G(P, q|X_{n'}, a_{n,1}^{S_n}) \\
&= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{n'=1}^N \beta(n, n') G(P, q|X_{n'}, a_{n,1}^{S_n}) \\
&= \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{n'=1}^N \frac{\beta(n, n')}{N} \sum_{s=1}^{S_n+1} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{V}^+} P(a|a_{n,1}^{s-1}, X_{n'}) \log \frac{P(a|a_{n,1}^{s-1}, X_{n'})}{q_\theta(a|a_{n,1}^{s-1})}
\end{aligned}$$

The derivation is done and we have shown that Eq. (9) and (10) are equivalent.